

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Berete**FIRST NAME:** Ansoumane**PROGRAM CODE:** DEPI**COURSE CODE:** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Gulma**Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List 5 to 7 critical concepts with page numbers in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Introduction (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 1-2)
2. Process of academic essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 2)
3. The structure of the academic essay (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3)
4. The rules of academic essay writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3)
5. What is a style guide (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3)
6. Plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 3-4)
7. Conclusion

ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

This first period gives students a comprehensive knowledge of essay writing, punctuation, America vs. British English, plagiarism, style guide, CMS crib sheet, Latin abbreviations and expressions, and a sample correction of response paper. These chapters mentioned above gave the students a broad view of drafting academic documents in a globally acceptable manner.

The book describes the different academic essay writing processes, starting with the problem definition, obtaining the sources, reading and thinking critically, organizing the essay, and writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

Writing an essay requires a transparent methodology; the author summarizes the key ideas from the body section and restates their opinion regarding the question or writing assignment in the conclusion part (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 10).

Rules govern academic essay writing to guarantee that writers convey ideas. Punctuation and language variations are two crucial guidelines that help with efficient and consistent academic essay writing. Sentences acquire meanings through punctuation. The apostrophe, for instance, indicates that a word or pronoun is single or indefinite. In English, contractions of two words are also expressed using apostrophes. The bullet sign is employed in lists of words, phrases, or clauses that make up sentences. The placement of colons and semi-colons determines the meanings of various sentence portions. The colon joins independent parts of a sentence, whereas the semi-colon joins two linked parts. There are several ways to use commas in sentences to communicate meaning (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 12).

2) PROCESS OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

Academic writing involves a procedure, much like writing other kinds of essays. The steps involved in producing an academic or scholarly essay are defining the problem, obtaining sources, reading and thinking critically, organizing the essay, and writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7–14). I have learned from the text that clarifying and evaluating the current writing assignment is wise. This phase could involve mentally evaluating one's prior knowledge of the subject. Additionally, it can entail examining preliminary ideas regarding the topic at hand (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7).

Acquiring materials that elaborate on the writing work comes after comprehending and identifying its topic. Academic essays require different resources than other essays due to their scholarly background.

3) THE STRUCTURE OF ACADEMIC ESSAYS

Academic writings are guided by structures and frameworks that help writers convey their thoughts clearly and consistently. The format recommended by EUCLID consists of an introduction, a body, and a conclusion. Academic essay writers are encouraged to incorporate information such as a brief topic orientation in the beginning part. Positional comments on the subject and an overview of the structure of the other parts are among the additional recommended information included in the introduction section (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 7–10).

The academic essay's body comprises the specifics of the major points, supporting facts, an examination of the supporting data, and transitional phrases to the subsequent body part. The appropriate division of these concepts into significant thought portions (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 11).

There are other possible structures of essay writing depending on the institution's culture and the nature of the topic. In some institutions, like EUCLID, the introduction forms the essay's central idea. The paragraphs include the arguments or subpoints that support the points you are making. Depending on the length of your essay, you may need

fewer or more of these body paragraphs. The critical notion from the introduction is essentially reiterated in the conclusion (Victoria University 2015, 1).

In the body, you provide a detailed explanation and defense of the arguments you made in the introduction for your point of view using evidence from academic readings. The essay comprises several paragraphs that work together to create a compelling case or discussion of the subject. A paragraph should typically consist of four to six phrases. In an academic essay, a single sentence does not constitute a paragraph, and bullet points are generally inappropriate (Te Pukenga, n.d.).

4) THE RULES OF ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

According to the ACA-401 Coursepack, utilizing a selected English language variant in academic writing promotes uniformity and meaning. The American and British varieties are the more well-known. Some terms in these two notable versions may be spelled differently, but the pronunciations are the same, or vice versa. Furthermore, even when two words have the exact spelling, their usage in different situations might give them different meanings. The use of punctuation, collective nouns, and plural adjectives is another variation (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 25).

5) WHAT IS A STYLE GUIDE

You can use a style guide to record how you, as a writer, handle particular aspects of writing style that must be maintained consistently. Style guides are typically linked to specific writing genres, such as web copywriting, technical writing, journalism, and commercial or business writing (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 41).

It is necessary to ensure that the writing style is consistent in each situation. Therefore, rules are typically released to enable multiple authors to participate while guaranteeing that the final product does not necessarily reflect the writer's unique style but rather that of the publication, business, or website linked to the writing. A style guide is necessary for firms or magazines with many contributing authors if the final product is to be coherent.

I have written academic articles in the past, and the significant observations are that French-speaking and English-speaking instructions have different style guides given to students or researchers to draft essays, theses, or documents. It also varies based on where the researcher wishes to publish the essay

6) PLAGIARISM

When a writer borrows knowledge from another source without citing the original author, it is considered plagiarism (Cleenewerck and Gulma 2021, 34).

Plagiarism Examples: Use someone else's words or ideas without giving them credit, such as when you quote, paraphrase, copy, and paste something from the internet. Plagiarism would occur if you had someone create a paper for you, sign it with your name, and turn it in to your professor.

The course pack provides detailed information on how to cite the authors to avoid plagiarism clearly

In every academic institution, plagiarism is a highly intellectual and ethical offense

7) **CONCLUSION**

Specific procedures, guidelines, and standards regulate academic paper development and presentation. The student must understand the process of creating an academic essay and its structure. The student should also know the guidelines for avoiding plagiarism, how to use and adhere to a style guide while creating academic papers, and how to communicate ideas using punctuation and different English language varieties.

REFERENCES

Victoria University. 2015. "A Typical Structure for an Academic Essay." <https://www.vu.edu.au/current-students/campus-life/advice-support/learning-advice>.

Laurent, Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.

Te Pukenga. 2024. "Writing an Academic Essay." <https://www.ecampusnz.com/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.